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- ✓ IJTIMOIIY FANLAR

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FEATURES OF CROHN'S DISEASE IN A CHILD WITH CONGENITAL SOMATOTROPIC INSUFFICIENCY

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Annotation. *A patient with congenital hypopituitarism is under observation at the SFRSNPCE. Growth hormone (GH) deficiency was confirmed by diagnostic stimulation tests (maximum peak GH value - 8.3 ng/ml). At diagnosis, the growth deficit was -3.9 SDS. MRI diagnosed an “empty sella turcica”, a heterogeneous structure of the pituitary gland. No dysfunction of other endocrine glands was detected. Bone age was 4 years behind the passport age and was 9 years. Somatogenic causes of growth retardation and chromosomal abnormalities were excluded. A study of genes associated with hypopituitarism did not reveal mutations. Therapy with GH drugs was started at a daily dose of 0.033 mg per 1 kg of body weight. 2 months after the start of replacement therapy, the patient was hospitalized in the surgical department of the hospital with symptoms of “acute abdomen”. GH therapy was suspended. Upon further examination, a diagnosis was made: Crohn's disease. After surgical treatment and prescription of specific therapy with Remicade according to the regimen, GH treatment was resumed (the break was 6 months). Currently, the patient is receiving GH replacement therapy and ongoing therapy for the concomitant disease, Crohn's disease.*

Keywords: *congenital hypopituitarism, Crohn's disease, somatotrophic insufficiency, growth hormone, clinical case.*

ОСОБЕННОСТИ БОЛЕЗНИ КРОНА У РЕБЕНКА С ВРОЖДЕННОЙ СОМАТОТРОПНОЙ НЕДОСТАТОЧНОСТЬЮ

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Аннотация. В ГФРСНПХ под наблюдением находится больной с врожденным гипопитуитаризмом. Дефицит гормона роста (ГР) подтверждался диагностическими тестами стимуляции (максимальное пиковое значение ГР - 8,3 нг/мл). На момент постановки диагноза дефицит роста составил -3,9 SDS. При МРТ диагностировано «пустое турецкое седло» — неоднородная структура гипофиза. Нарушений со стороны других эндокринных желез не выявлено. Костный возраст отставал от паспортного на 4 года и составлял 9 лет. Соматогенные причины задержки роста и хромосомные аномалии были исключены. Исследование генов, связанных с гипопитуитаризмом, не выявило мутаций. Терапию препаратами ГР начинали в суточной дозе 0,033 мг на 1 кг массы тела. Через 2 месяца после начала заместительной терапии больной госпитализирован в хирургическое отделение больницы с симптомами «острого живота». Терапия ГР была приостановлена. При дальнейшем обследовании поставлен диагноз: болезнь Крона. После хирургического лечения и назначения специфической терапии Ремикейдом по схеме лечение ГР возобновили (перерыв составил 6 мес). В настоящее время пациентка получает заместительную терапию гормоном роста и продолжает терапию сопутствующего заболевания - болезни Крона.

Ключевые слова: врожденный гипопитуитаризм, болезнь Крона, соматотропная недостаточность, гормон роста, клинический случай.

Introduction. Diagnosis of congenital somatotrophic deficiency, based on the study of stimulated secretion of growth hormone (GH), makes it possible to verify the disease and determine the need for growth-stimulating therapy with GH drugs [1]. The use of GH for short stature against the background of severe immunologically mediated disorders requires special caution. Somatropin is an effective and safe drug in children with GH deficiency [2, 3]. However, it is impossible to predict the occurrence of any concomitant diseases in a particular patient during GH therapy, the provoking cause of which could be the start of replacement therapy. Description of the case A girl born in 2002 is under the supervision of a pediatric endocrinologist at the SFRSNPTSE. For the first time, an endocrinologist was contacted in 2015 at the age of 13 years with complaints about low growth rates from an early age (in the 1st year of life she grew by 17 cm, in the years preceding the examination the growth rate did not exceed 4 cm per year). Growth retardation was associated with constitutional characteristics and somatic causes. Thus, from the age of 11, she was observed by a rheumatologist due to joint pain. Pain in the left hip and left ankle joints was regarded as manifestations of reactive arthritis, Schlatter's disease. At the age of 13 years, she was examined in an endocrinology hospital for short stature. The growth SDS was -3.9. Stimulation tests revealed a decrease in peak GH values: the maximum release was 8.3 ng/ml. Thus, the diagnosis of somatotrophic insufficiency was confirmed. The MR picture did not exclude the presence of a pituitary microadenoma; An empty sella turcica and a heterogeneous structure of the pituitary gland were diagnosed. No dysfunction of other endocrine glands was detected. Bone age was 4 years behind the passport age and was 9 years. Somatogenic causes of growth retardation and chromosomal abnormalities were excluded. A molecular genetic study of genes associated with hypopituitarism did not reveal mutations. Therapy with GH drugs was started at a daily dose of 0.033 mg per 1 kg of body weight. 2 months after the start of GH therapy, the patient was hospitalized with suspected acute appendicitis. During emergency surgery, the diagnosis was confirmed; Appendectomy and resection of the inflammatory strand of the omentum were performed. Histologically, phlegmonous appendicitis, peritonitis, and mesenteriolitis were revealed. Somatropin therapy was temporarily suspended. 3 days after discharge from the hospital, the patient experienced severe abdominal pain, fever, and an infiltrate in the right iliac region. Upon re-hospitalization, ultrasound and CT scanning of the abdominal cavity diagnosed terminal ileitis, omentitis, interintestinal abscess, and ileal diverticulum. Antibacterial therapy was prescribed. When examined 1 month

after re-hospitalization, persistent signs of systemic inflammation were found, caused by an infiltrate in the abdominal cavity of 10-15 cm without abscess formation, inflammatory changes in the terminal ileum, sharp thickening of the walls of the small intestine with a narrowing of the lumen to 3 mm, signs of proximal intestinal dilatation. The diagnosis of Crohn's disease was confirmed by serological examination data: an increase in ASCA of both classes, an increase in calprotectin to 607. Analysis of the NOD2/CARD15 gene for the receptor for muramyl dipeptide (a component of the bacterial cell wall) revealed a genetic risk for Crohn's disease. The girl received long-term antibacterial therapy (thienam, ceftazidime, amikacin, cefepime). Considering the penetrating form of the disease with the development of complications, specific therapy with the drug Remicade was carried out. Due to severe growth retardation and the high risk of surgical treatment, it was decided to abstain from steroid therapy. During the therapy, a decrease in the size of the infiltrate was observed, but high laboratory activity and an increase in temperature remained. A diagnostic laparoscopy was performed. An area of altered intestine was identified, laparotomy was performed, and the ileocecal angle of the intestine was resected. The postoperative period was uneventful. Remicade therapy was continued. After 6 months, treatment with GH drugs was resumed at a dose of 0.033 mg/kg/day. During therapy, the level of IGF-I (December 2016) was 282 ng/ml. Levels of thyroid and adrenal hormones are within normal limits. During 6 months of replacement therapy after surgery, the increase in height was 4 cm, height SDS was 4.07. Discussion The complexity of the described case is determined by two factors. The first is associated with the diagnosis of hypopituitarism (or somatotrophic insufficiency). Is this the primary disease against which Crohn's disease manifested itself, or did a genetically determined disease with an immunopathological mechanism of development, Crohn's disease, manifest itself in the child with progressive growth retardation with impaired GH secretion? The second and most difficult question is the possibility of continuing GH treatment. The coincidence of the start of growth-stimulating therapy and the manifestation of Crohn's disease determines the need for a balanced approach to continuing GH treatment. Taking into account the significant growth retardation and stable somatic condition during treatment with Remicade, it was decided to continue GH therapy under the control of IGF-1 levels. specific therapy with the drug Remicade was carried out. Due to severe growth retardation and the high risk of surgical treatment, it was decided to abstain from steroid therapy. During the therapy, a decrease in the size of the infiltrate was observed, but high laboratory activity and an increase in temperature

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Conclusion. Growth hormone replacement therapy for congenital hypopituitarism is necessary. However, when prescribing somatropin, it is necessary to take into account the presence of concomitant diseases in patients, the manifestation of which can be provoked by replacement therapy. The safety of using growth hormone in children has been proven, but careful monitoring of the patient is required in each specific case.

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Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 03. 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 03. 2024	Том 02. Вып. 03. 2024

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Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 03. 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 03. 2024	Том 02. Вып. 03. 2024

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